

Information Sheet and Consent Form Template (for Low Risk Informatics Student Projects with Human Participants)

Invitation to take part

You are being invited to take part in a research study to further our understanding of a Maturity Model for Data Spaces. Thank you for carefully reading the following information. This study is being conducted by student researcher Julian Roloff doing a degree in Information Studies at the University of Amsterdam.

What is the purpose of this research?

This research aims to develop a maturity model to assess and improve the organizational and business capabilities of data spaces.

What is involved in taking part?

Participants will be asked to review and evaluate a proposed maturity model for data spaces that is based on the DSSC's Organizational and Business Building Blocks. This evaluation involves completing a structured assessment form with both quantitative ratings and qualitative feedback on the model's clarity, relevance, and usability. Data collected will include Likert-scale responses and open-text comments.

Is participation voluntary?

Your participation is voluntary, and you can choose to take part in only certain parts of the study, or not at all. You may withdraw from the research at any time and without providing a reason, in which case, we will not use your data and will destroy it immediately. After having taken part in the study, you can still withdraw consent and request the removal of your data up until the start of data analysis. To do so, please email julian.roloff@student.uva.nl and include your full name.

How will my data be treated?

Data will be anonymized such that it is not possible to identify you. Data will be stored securely (e.g. for paper-based data, in a locked filing cabinet or for digital data, on an encrypted or password-protected server). Furthermore, no data (anonymised or otherwise) will be used as input to Generative AI tools (e.g. ChatGPT). In line with GDPR and relevant regulations, the data will be kept for one year after data collection, after which it will be destroyed. (optional) Anonymised data may also be submitted to the Open Science Foundation (OSF) in the interests of open science.

Questions or Concerns:

If you have any questions about the study, please feel free to contact the student researcher: Julian Roloff, julian.roloff@student.uva.nl. You can also contact the student's supervisor: Thomas van Binsbergen, t.t.vanbinsbergen.uva.nl.

Declaration of Consent

I confirm that I:

- am 18 years or over
• have read and understood the provided information
• agree to participate in this study
• consent to the use of the resulting data as described above
• consent to the research team carrying out further analysis of my anonymised data (tick here if you agree) _____

Name of participant

Signature of participant

Date